

Infrared Studies of Mono-substituted Copper(II) Benzoates. Influence of pK_a , Polarisability, Mesomeric Effect and Steric Effect

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In *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-substituted nitro-, chloro- and methyl-compounds of copper(II) benzoates, the increase or decrease of antisymmetric COO stretching frequencies has been correlated with pK_a , polarisability, mesomeric effect and steric effect.

Lewis and Thompson^{1,2} have studied the magnetic moment of nitro-, chloro- and methyl-substituted copper(II) benzoates and these measurements were correlated with the pK_a of the parent organic acid, polarisability of the ligand and steric effect. Srivastava³ has studied the influence of these factors in copper(II) haloacetates. But practically no attempt has been made in which the influence of these factors could be shown on the carboxylate group vibrations, *i.e.* ν_{as} (COO) and ν_s (COO), and consequently on their molecular structures, by ir study, in the mono-substituted benzoates. Therefore, we have proposed to study the influence of these factors including the contribution of mesomeric effect on COO group vibrations and thus on the antisymmetric and symmetric COO stretching frequencies. The approach of discussion can be summarised as follows.

The spin-spin interaction of adjacent Cu^{II} ions occurs by direct overlap *via* bridging carboxyl groups⁴. The type of variation of this metal-metal interaction has been discussed by Nyholm⁴ and Lewis *et al.*^{1,2}. These authors correlated this interaction with the polarisability of the ligands and direct in terms of the available σ -electron density on the carboxylate oxygen atoms. This variation in the interaction found for the copper(II) complexes can, therefore, be correlated with the ligand polarisability and it can be suggested that more polarisable ligands reduce the effective positive charge on Cu^{II} ions and allow a favourable overlap of the metal orbitals.

The pK_a of the parent acids can be taken as a measure of the polarisability on the ligand and could, therefore, be correlated with the electron donation power of the carboxylate oxygen atoms to the metal ions⁵.

A carboxylic acid may bond to copper ions to form the complexes in one of the following three ways⁶.

The (a) type structure holds the Cu^{II} ions close enough together to allow the possibility of direct Cu-Cu interaction. Furthermore, it is clear that the repulsion between the metal ions is significant thus will increase as the effective positive charge on the metal increases. In structure (a), a greater electron transfer to the Cu^{II} ions makes their d-orbitals larger and reduces their effective positive charge. This less effective positive charge reduces the repulsion between the Cu-atoms and increases the possibility of larger overlap of the d-orbitals between them. Stronger acids than benzoic acid are less polarisable (low pK_a) and thus have lower σ -electron density available for Cu-atoms. This greater residual positive charge on Cu^{II} ions produces enough repulsion between them. The Cu-atoms will move apart at a lower distance but the dimeric structure still retained. In the structures (b) and (c), the Cu-atoms have more residual positive charge than in structure (a) and, therefore, the more repulsion between them and a larger distance of separation.

Experimental

All the compounds were prepared by the reported methods⁷.

Ortho-, *meta*- and *para*-nitrobenzoic acids (Ward Benkingsop), *o*-chlorobenzoic acid (Koch-light); *m*- and *p*-chlorobenzoic acids, *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-methylbenzoic acids (Fluka); and pure pellets of NaOH and crystalline $CuSO_4$ (AnalaR) were used. The ir

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TABLE I

Compd.	ν_{as} (COO) cm^{-1}	ν_s (COO) cm^{-1}	pK_a^*	Magnetic moment (μ)** B.M.	P/D†
Cu benzoate	1560	1405	4.18	1.37	D
Cu <i>o</i> -nitrobenzoate (monohydrate)	1602	1400	3.21	1.87	P
Cu <i>m</i> -nitrobenzoate	1598	1390	3.47	1.67	P
Cu <i>p</i> -nitrobenzoate	1596	1410	3.40	1.59	P
Cu <i>o</i> -chlorobenzoate	1592	1392	2.89	1.63	P, D
Cu <i>m</i> -chlorobenzoate	1538	1385	3.80	1.92	D
Cu <i>p</i> -chlorobenzoate	1538	1410	4.05	1.42	D
Cu <i>o</i> -methylbenzoate	1540	1390	3.92	1.41	D
Cu <i>m</i> -methylbenzoate	1565	1385	4.25	1.69	P
Cu <i>p</i> -methylbenzoate	1556	1405	4.35	1.36	D

* Ref. 2. ** Ref. 1. † P=Polymeric and D=dimeric.

spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Parkin-Elmer 177 spectrophotometer over the range 4000-200 cm^{-1} .

Results and Discussion

Antisymmetric COO and symmetric COO stretching frequencies of *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-substituted nitro-, chloro- and methyl-benzoates of copper(II) are presented in the Table I. The magnetic moment (μ) and pK_a values are taken from the literature^{1,2}. The polymeric (P) and dimeric (D) structures were proposed earlier^{1,6} on the basis of magnetic moment data, ν_{as} (COO), ν_s (COO) and ΔE .

From the above discussion it is obvious that the ligands of low polarisability or low pK_a of the parent acid or in general higher electronegativity of R group do not have enough σ -electron density available at oxygen in the COO group for bonding with the Cu^{II} ions. Thus the effective positive charge over Cu^{II} ions is not decreased considerably and a large degree of repulsion exists between the Cu^{II} ions which leads towards a compound having an asymmetric COO group and in the extreme case of repulsion the structure may be polymeric monodentate or bidentate type. The bidentate structure,

(COO) and ν_s (COO) should shift in the same direction upon substitution and their ΔE , the difference of ν_{as} (COO) and ν_s (COO), should be in the range of symmetric compounds. Therefore, it is expected that in the monodentate compounds the asymmetric frequency of COO group should increase with the decrease of pK_a value due to asymmetric type of COO bondings.

If the ν_{as} (COO) of *o*-nitro-, *o*-chloro- and *o*-methyl-substituted copper(II) benzoates are compared, then it is observed that the lower ν_{as} (COO) of *o*-methyl (1540 cm^{-1}) than *o*-chloro (1592 cm^{-1}) and *o*-nitro (1602 cm^{-1}) is due to its higher pK_a (3.92) than *o*-chloro (2.89) and *o*-nitro (3.21). The higher ν_{as} (COO) of *o*-nitro than

o-chloro is unexpected as it has higher pK_a than *o*-chloro. It is an established fact⁷ that the steric effect plays an important role amongst *ortho*-substituted compounds than *meta*- and *para*-substituted compounds. As discussed elsewhere¹ that most of the *ortho*-benzoates are dimeric compounds due to steric effect. Here, only *o*-methyl-substituted is fully dimeric. The *o*-chloro-substituted shows dimeric and polymeric behaviour together, while the *o*-nitro-substituted compound is purely of polymeric type. This polymeric nature is fully justified by the magnetic moment value (1.87 B.M.) almost in the same range of 1.9-2.0 B.M. for other normal copper salts. In this *o*-nitro compound, it appears that the polar effect of nitro group has masked the steric effect. Similar masking effect of nitro-group has been observed by Goldschmidt⁸. Due to this predominant polar effect, *o*-nitrobenzoate is polymeric and has got a high asymmetric frequency of 1602 cm^{-1} .

If the *m*-substituted nitro-, chloro- and methyl-benzoates are compared on the basis of their increasing pK_a values then it is expected that asymmetric COO frequency should follow, nitro > chloro > methyl. The lower pK_a (3.47) and accordingly higher asymmetric COO frequency (1598 cm^{-1}) of *m*-nitro compound than *m*-chloro and *m*-methyl is probably due to an electron withdrawing inductive effect (-I) of nitro group. But the order is reversed in chloro- and methyl-substituted compounds. This can be due to more steric effect for chloro- than for methyl-substituted compound, presuming the size of the group as the mass of the group⁹.

Amongst the *para*-substituted compounds there is a pronounced electron withdrawing mesomeric effect (-M) in nitro compound while an electron donating mesomeric effect (+M) in chloro compound. Hence, nitro compound is stronger ($pK_a = 3.40$) than the chloro ($pK_a = 4.05$), and consequently *p*-nitro has got higher ν_{as} (COO) (1596 cm^{-1}) than *p*-chloro (1538 cm^{-1}). Again, *p*- CH_3 is weaker ($pK_a = 4.35$) than *p*-Cl ($pK_a = 4.05$), probably due to pronounced electron donating hyperconju-

gative effect of methyl group in *p*-methyl compound. But it is observed that the asymmetric COO frequency of *p*-chloro is lower (1538 cm^{-1}) than *p*-methyl (1556 cm^{-1}). In fact, we did not stress very much on this irregularity because the $\nu_{as}(\text{COO})$ of chloro compound is little ambiguous as mentioned earlier⁶.

If *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-substituted nitro-, chloro- and methyl-benzoates are compared separately, then in the case of nitrobenzoates it is observed that the strength of *o*-nitro is considerably greater ($pK_a=3.21$) than *m*-nitro ($pK_a=3.47$) and *p*-nitro ($pK_a=3.40$) compounds, and accordingly *o*-nitro should have higher $\nu_{as}(\text{COO})$ frequency than *m*- and *p*-benzoates. But only a little increase of $\nu_{as}(\text{COO})$ in *ortho*- than *meta*- and *para*-compounds is observed. This unexpected behaviour of *o*-nitro may be due to the influence of steric effect and, therefore, only a little increase could be seen. The greater strength of *o*-nitrobenzoate can be due to, (i) direct interaction of adjacent group and (ii) pronounced inductive effect

Both *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzoates are equally acidic having pK_a 3.47 and 3.40, respectively and consequently they have got nearly the same $\nu_{as}(\text{COO})$ i.e. 1598 and 1596 cm^{-1} , respectively. This is because in *m*-nitro there is a pronounced electron withdrawing inductive effect ($-I$) while in *p*-nitro there should be negligible inductive effect but a pronounced electron withdrawing mesomeric effect ($-M$). Amongst the chlorobenzoates, lower pK_a and higher $\nu_{as}(\text{COO})$ of *o*-chloro than *m*- and *p*- may be due to molecular overcrowding in *o*-chloro-compound. *m*-Chloro is stronger ($pK_a=3.80$) than

p-chloro ($pK_a=4.05$) because there is an electron withdrawing inductive effect ($-I$) more pronounced in *m*-Cl than in *p*-Cl, and an electron donating mesomeric effect ($+M$) only in the case of *p*-Cl. But both *m*- and *p*-chloro compounds have got the same $\nu_{as}(\text{COO})$ (1538 cm^{-1}). There appears some anomaly in the assignment of $\nu_{as}(\text{COO})$ of *p*-Cl which has been mentioned earlier⁶. In the case of methylbenzoates it is observed that *o*-CH₃ has pK_a lower (3.92) than *m*-CH₃ (4.25) but the asymmetric frequency of *m*-CH₃ (1565 cm^{-1}) is higher than *o*-CH₃ (1540 cm^{-1}). This unexpected decrease in frequency of *ortho*-compound may be due to the predominant steric effect. In *m*-CH₃, greater strength ($pK_a=4.25$) and accordingly higher $\nu_{as}(\text{COO})$, i.e. 1565 cm^{-1} *p*-CH₃ (having $pK_a=4.35$ and $\nu_{as}(\text{COO})$ 1556 cm^{-1}), may be due to the pronounced hyperconjugative effect of methyl group in *p*-methylbenzoate.

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